

Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of Cu (II), Ni (II), Co (II) and Fe(II) with *o*-Hydroxyketoanils

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The stability constants of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(II) complexes with (i) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propio-phenone-ethylenediamineanil (HMPEA), (ii) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl benzophenone-ethylenediamineanil (HMBEA) and (iii) 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone-ethylenediamineanil (HCBEA) have been determined potentiometrically in water dioxane 50% v/v medium at $\mu = 0.2 M$, NaClO_4 at 25°. It is observed that the order of stability of the chelates is in agreement with Irving-Williams order. The effect of change in structure of the ligand on proton-ligand stability constant has been discussed. The change in free energy of complex formation has been calculated.

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC study on complex formation between Fe(II) and 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone-ethylene diamine anil (HMBEA) has been reported¹. The present work deals with the determination of stability constants of some metal chelates in water-dioxane medium (50% v/v). The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were determined by the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti^{2,3}.

Experimental

Preparation of Reagents :

The reagents (i) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propio-phenone-ethylenediamineanil (HMPEA), (ii) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl - benzophenone - ethylenediamineanil (HMBEA), and (iii) 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-benzophenone-ethylenediamineanil (HCBEA) are prepared by refluxing 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propio-phenone, 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone and 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone, respectively with ethylenediamine in 2:1 molar proportion in ethanol, when yellow anils are obtained. They are recrystallised from ethanol. They are represented in the general structure (Fig.) 1.

Fig. 1: *o*-Hydroxyketoanil

- i) HMPEA : R = $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$; R' = $-\text{CH}_3$
- ii) HMBEA : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; R' = $-\text{CH}_3$
- iii) HCBEA : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; R' = $-\text{Cl}$.

The reagent solutions ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) are prepared in pure dioxane and the stock solutions of Cu(II),

Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(II), each of concentration $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ are prepared in double distilled water and standardised by the general methods⁷. All the metal salts used were of B.D.H. Anal. R quality.

Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (0.5M) was prepared by a standard technique and was standardised potentiometrically against potassium phthalate. The stock solutions of sodium perchlorate (1.0M) and perchloric acid (1.0M) was prepared, by dissolving Anal. R sample of $\text{NaClO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Riedel) and HClO_4 (E. Merck). The concentration of perchloric acid was determined by titrating it potentiometrically against sodium hydroxide. A pH meter (Systronic) with glass electrode (0-13 pH) and saturated calomel electrode was used. It was calibrated with aqueous buffers of pH 4.0 and 9.18.

Proton-ligand and Metal-ligand Stability Constants :

The experimental procedure involved titration of (i) free HClO_4 (0.025M), (ii) free HClO_4 (0.025M) + reagent ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$), (iii) free HClO_4 (0.025M) + reagent ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) + metal ion ($3.75 \times 10^{-4} M$), against standard NaOH solution (0.5M) added from the burette. The initial total volume in each case was 40 ml and water dioxane composition 50% v/v was maintained. The ionic strength was maintained constant $\mu = 0.2 M$ with 1.0M NaClO_4 . The pH meter readings B are recorded. The meter reading B converted to corresponding pH by the method suggested by Van Uitert and Hass⁴ using the relation $B = \text{pH} - \log UH$.

The pH are plotted against the volume of alkali added. The ligand proton formation number of degree of formation \bar{n}_A was obtained by using Irving-Rossotti expression⁵ considering the total number of replaceable protons per ligand molecule $Y = 2$. The ligand-proton formation curve was then obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A against pH. The proton-ligand stability constants are determined by the methods⁶ (a) inter-

polation at half \bar{n}_A values and (b) by linear plot method. The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Sr. No.	Ligand	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$
1.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-propiofenone-ethylene-diamineanil (HMPEA)	*9.32 **9.30 Mean = 9.31	4.45 4.35 4.40
2.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone-ethylene-diamineanil (HMBEA)	*9.41 **9.38 Mean = 9.39	4.48 4.28 4.38
3.	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-benzophenone-ethylene-diamineanil (HCBEA)	*10.42 **10.22 Mean = 10.32	5.40 5.32 5.36

* Proton-ligand stability constants calculated at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ directly from the formation curve.

** Proton-ligand stability constants calculated by linear plot method.

The metal-ligand formation number, \bar{n} , and free ligand exponent pL are calculated using Irving-Rossotti expression⁶ and the metal-ligand formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL. The maximum value of \bar{n} is nearly one and indicates 1 : 1 complex. The metal ligand stability constants are determined at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ value directly from the formation curves and by linear plot method. The change in free energy ΔG was calculated using the relation $\Delta G = -RT \ln K$. The results are recorded in Table 2.

Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constant values for 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propiofenone-ethylenediamineanil and 2-hydroxy-5-methyl benzophenone-ethylenediamineanil are nearly equal suggest that the inductive effect of phenyl group or propyl group at carbonyl carbon is very less on hydroxy group in benzene ring. This may be due to the fact that this substitution is not directly linked with the benzene ring having

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 25°

Sr. No.	Ligand	Metal ion	$\log K$			$-\Delta G$ k.cal/mole degree
			*	**	Mean	
1.	HMPEA	Cu ²⁺	7.68	7.62	7.65	10.44
2.	HMPEA	Ni ²⁺	6.88	6.80	6.84	9.33
3.	HMPEA	Co ²⁺	6.39	6.21	6.30	8.59
4.	HMPEA	Fe ²⁺	6.00	6.12	6.06	8.26
5.	HMBEA	Cu ²⁺	7.70	7.68	7.69	10.49
6.	HMBEA	Ni ²⁺	6.95	6.84	6.89	9.40
7.	HMBEA	Co ²⁺	6.40	6.42	6.41	8.74
8.	HMBEA	Fe ²⁺	6.15	6.25	6.20	8.46
9.	HCBEA	Cu ²⁺	8.96	8.48	8.72	11.89
10.	HCBEA	Ni ²⁺	8.32	8.12	8.22	11.21
11.	HCBEA	Co ²⁺	7.56	7.45	7.50	10.23
12.	HCBEA	Fe ²⁺	7.46	7.22	7.34	10.01

* Stability constants calculated at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ from the formation curve.

** Stability constants calculated by linear plot method.

-OH group. The proton-ligand stability constant for 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-benzophenone-ethylenediamineanil is higher which is due to the inductive effect of chloro group para to -OH group. The chloro group being electronegative has increased the acidic character of phenolic -OH group. The increasing order of stability constants of metal chelates are in the order Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Fe²⁺ which is in agreement with Irving Williams order.

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